

Autonomous extraction and building of machine-readable molecular models from publications using large language models

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Abstract

Force field models are one of the central elements of molecular simulations. A large number of molecular force field models has been developed in the past decades – mostly published in scientific papers. Building machine readable force field input files for simulation engines is a tedious and error-prone task. We developed a method for autonomously extracting and building force field files from publications using large language models (LLM). We have tested the new method by extracting 114 force field models from 21 scientific publications. The studied force fields comprise 6 - 74 parameters. We have compared the performance of different LLMs, namely Gemini 2.5 Pro, Claude 4 Sonnet, GPT-4o, Claude 3.7 Sonnet, and Gemini 2.5 Flash. Overall,

they yield a similar performance – yet, important differences in individual cases. The overall best performance was obtained by the Gemini 2.5 Pro LLM. The force field parameters were extracted and identified with an accuracy of 89.1% by the Gemini 2.5 Pro LLM. The new autonomous extraction method drastically reduces the time required for building force field files – and does not depend on the experience of the simulator.

Introduction

Simulations based on molecular models are a powerful tool that enable the prediction of macroscopic thermophysical properties as well as for the modeling of nanoscopic processes. Classical molecular simulations, i.e. molecular dynamics (MD) and Monte Carlo (MC) simulation, have become a standard tool in many scientific disciplines such as computational physics,¹⁻³ physical chemistry,⁴⁻⁷ tribology,⁸ molecular biology,⁹⁻¹³ astronomy,^{14,15} and chemical engineering.¹⁶⁻²¹

Matter is modeled in MD and MC simulations using molecular models – so-called force fields – that describe the interactions on the atomistic level. In MD simulations, the force fields are used to calculate the actual forces between interaction sites such that the trajectories of the interaction sites over a given time period can be computed. In MC simulations, the potential energy is used for evaluating the probability for existence of a given atomistic configuration by computing the total potential energy. Thereby, a force field mathematically describes the molecular interactions. Molecular simulations can have impressive predictive capabilities – which facilitates their popularity. Nevertheless, the predictive capabilities depend on the quality of the employed force field.²²⁻²⁹ Moreover, it has been emphasized that the successful reproducibility of predictions from molecular simulations strongly depends on accurate force field models and that even minor mistakes by users can have severe consequences for the results.³⁰⁻³² Reducing the influence of the simulator as error source upon building force field files and standardizing work flows is desirable.³²⁻³⁵

A large number of force fields have been proposed in the past decades, e.g. Refs.^{36–39} Moreover, various MD/MC simulation engines are in use today, e.g. Refs.^{40,40–42,42–47} For employing a given force field in a simulation engine, machine readable force field input files are required. Force field models have been published mostly in classical journal articles in the past decades. In most cases, the force field specifications are reported in the main .pdf file of a given publication. Often, the information and data defining a given force field is spread across different entities, i.e. figures, tables, text etc., of a paper. Force field models are often described in text and tables, whereas ready-to-use simulation files are practically never provided in publications (partly due to the lack of standardized force field file formats). Moreover, a publication may report one or multiple force field models for one or more molecules and/ or different molecules, with relevant details either consolidated (e.g. in a table) or scattered throughout the text, sometimes using different potential forms or unit systems. In some cases, relevant information might be included in a graphic such as geometry details. Building force field input files 'by hand' by simulators is a tedious and error-prone task. While some force field databases exist, e.g. the MolMod database,^{36,37} that provide input files for simulation engines, these databases comprise only a fraction of the models available in the literature. Presently force field models are not available under FAIR conditions.⁴⁸ Digitizing, annotating, and depositing force fields in databases is still in its infancy. In this work, we propose a methodology for autonomously digitizing force field models from scientific publications using large language models (LLM).

LLMs have gained significant attention across a wide range of natural language processing (NLP) tasks in both academia and industry.^{49,50} Their performance is being systematically evaluated in diverse applications to better assess their capabilities from multiple perspectives. It is evident that they will continue to play an increasingly important role at the societal level as their potential and associated risks are more thoroughly understood. A key advantage of LLMs, compared to traditional approaches, lies in their versatility to address a broad set of tasks within a single framework. Fundamentally, LLMs are large-scale neural

models trained on extensive text corpora to learn patterns of language, semantics, and context.^{51,52} The core technology underlying most LLMs is the self-attention mechanism within the transformer architecture, which serves as a foundational component for language-related tasks.⁵³ To date, LLMs have been successfully applied to tasks such as information extraction, semantic structuring, classification, summarization of unstructured data and beyond. These applications highlight their potential in the digitization and automated processing of documents and data.^{54,55}

In this work, we propose a novel methodology that introduces LLMs for the autonomous digitization of force field models. This new method is tested using five different LLMs and validated using a variety of force fields extracted from 21 publications from the literature. The results from the digitization are compared with force field files from a benchmark database. This paper is organized as follows: First, a brief introduction of force field models is given – focusing on aspects relevant for their digitization from publications. Then, the methodology for digitizing force field models from publications is presented. Third, the results from the case study based on 21 publications comprising 114 (component-specific rigid classical) force field models are presented and discussed. Finally, conclusions are drawn.

Structure of Molecular Force Field Models

There is a wide range of force field types available today. Force fields can be classified using different attributes, e.g. atomistic architecture (flexible or rigid), modeling approach (component-specific or transferable), model detail level (all-atom, united-atom, coarse grain), force field chemistry (reactive or non-reactive), underlying parametrization strategy (bottom-up or top-down), employed interaction potentials etc. An in-depth discussion is for example given in Ref.⁵⁶ In this work, classical (i.e. Newtonian) component-specific rigid force fields for molecules and ions are used for testing the new digitization method.

In classical force fields, the molecular interactions are modeled by interaction potentials

that describe the potential energy as a function of the spatial relations between two (or more particles/sites) $u(\underline{r})$. Despite the fact that these interaction potentials provide a relatively crude simplification of the 'true' molecular interactions, classical force fields have strong predictive capabilities.⁵⁷⁻⁶⁰ In classical molecular force field models, atoms (or groups of atoms) are represented as interaction sites, i.e. points in space. The interactions between these sites are described by the interaction potentials for which different ansatz functions exist, e.g. the Lennard-Jones potential, multipole interactions, etc. In rigid force field models, the interaction sites of a model have fixed relative positions. In flexible force fields, intramolecular degrees of freedom exist, which require additional interaction potentials. In this work, rigid force field models were used for testing the proposed digitization method. An interaction potential (both intermolecular and intramolecular) in a force field is specified by the general mathematical equation and the specific parameters applicable to the interactions under consideration. Moreover, the mass of each site needs to be specified. In summary, a force field consists of (a) the coordinates of the interaction sites and (b) the information on the interaction site type allocated to a given site, which is specified by the mathematical equation and the corresponding parameters. All this information has to be comprised in a well-defined way in force field files to be used by a simulation engine.

Intermolecular interactions are usually represented by dispersive-repulsive and electrostatic contributions. Dispersive-repulsive interactions between two particles i and j separated by a distance r_{ij} can for example be modeled by the Mie potential u_{Mie} (which is the generalized form of the Lennard-Jones (LJ) potential⁶¹) as

$$u_{\text{Mie}}(r_{ij}) = \frac{n}{n-m} \left(\frac{n}{m}\right)^{\frac{m}{n-m}} \varepsilon_{ij} \left[\left(\frac{\sigma_{ij}}{r_{ij}}\right)^n - \left(\frac{\sigma_{ij}}{r_{ij}}\right)^m \right], \quad (1)$$

where n and m denote the repulsive and dispersive exponents, respectively, ε_{ij} is the dispersion energy, and σ_{ij} is the size parameter of the interaction site. For the special case $n = 12$ and $m = 6$, the Mie potential reduces to the LJ potential.

Electrostatic interactions are commonly described using either point charges, point dipoles,

or point quadrupoles. For point charges, the electrostatic interaction is given by Coulomb's law⁶²

$$u_{ij}^{\text{qq}}(r_{ij}, q_i, q_j) = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{q_i q_j}{r_{ij}}, \quad (2)$$

where q_i and q_j describe the magnitude of the charge and r_{ij} the distance between the two charges.

Point dipoles describe the electrostatic field induced by two point charges with equal magnitude, but opposite sign. The interaction of two point dipoles is given by^{62,63}

$$u_{ij}^{\text{DD}}(r_{ij}, \theta_i, \theta_j, \phi_{ij}, \mu_i, \mu_j) = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{\mu_i \mu_j}{r_{ij}^3} \left(\sin \theta_i \sin \theta_j \cos \phi_{ij} - 2 \cos \theta_i \cos \theta_j \right), \quad (3)$$

where μ_i and μ_j describe the magnitude of the point dipoles, r_{ij} the distance between the two point dipoles and θ_i , θ_j , and ϕ_{ij} indicate the relative angular orientation of the two point dipoles.

Point quadrupoles describe the electrostatic field induced by either two collinear point dipoles with the same moment, but opposite orientation, or by at least three collinear point charges with alternating sign. The interaction potential of two quadrupole sites at a distance r_{ij} is given by^{63,64}

$$\begin{aligned} & u_{ij}^{\text{QQ}}(r_{ij}, \theta_i, \theta_j, \phi_{ij}, Q_i, Q_j) \\ &= \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{3}{4} \frac{Q_i Q_j}{r_{ij}^5} \left[1 - 5(\cos^2 \theta_i + \cos^2 \theta_j) - 15 \cos^2 \theta_i \cos^2 \theta_j \right. \\ & \quad \left. + 2(\sin \theta_i \sin \theta_j \cos \phi_{ij} - 4 \cos \theta_i \cos \theta_j)^2 \right], \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where Q_i and Q_j are the magnitude of the quadrupole moments, θ_i , θ_j , and ϕ_{ij} indicate

the relative angular orientation of the two point quadrupoles.⁶³

The number of parameters differs for the different interaction potentials, e.g. for a simple LJ potential, the two parameters ε_{ij} and σ_{ij} are required – each being a single scalar value (for a Mie potential, additionally m and n are required). For a point dipole, on the other hand, one scalar parameter value is required, namely the dipole moment μ , and one vector specifying its spatial orientation (θ and ϕ). An interaction site type is defined by its potential parameters together with the Cartesian coordinates (x, y, z) of the site, and additionally its mass.

These interaction site types are not exhaustive, but the vast majority of rigid force field models are built from these interaction potentials. The force field models used for testing the digitization method are built from the above listed interaction potentials.

Intramolecular interaction potentials define molecular flexibility and allow for vibrations within molecules. These include bond, angle, torsion, and improper torsion terms. A model in which the molecular geometry is fixed and no vibrations occur is referred to as 'rigid'. In the following, we restrict our approach to rigid models that incorporate both LJ and electrostatic interactions. Figure 1 illustrates two representative molecular force field models, namely for chlorine⁶⁵ and acetone.⁶⁶ A force field typically comprises the spatial coordinates of interaction sites (x, y, z) , the mass associated with each site (m), and interaction parameters required for the Mie/LJ and electrostatic potential functions $(\varepsilon, \sigma, m, n, \mu, Q)$. For implementation in molecular simulation engines, the force field description must usually conform to specific data formats, which may additionally require auxiliary information such as the number of sites assigned to each interaction type and which interaction type is applicable for a given model.

Force Field Digitization Method

The autonomous digitization method developed in this work extracts, transforms, identifies, and annotates information from scientific publications into simulation-ready force field input files. We use the `.pm` file format which is already in use within simulation engines as well as data curation infrastructure^{36,40} – an exemplary `.pm` file is given in the electronic Supporting Information. The digitization method consists of a sequence of five steps: (1) Optical character recognition (OCR), (2) text cleaning, (3) table detection, (4) data extraction, and (5) file generation. Each step is described in the following in detail, with an implementation provided in the electronic Supporting Information. An overview of the entire pipeline is shown in Figure 2 – in comparison to the classical manual approach. The goal of the workflow is to autonomously extract and identify force field parameters from publications, standardize them into a machine-readable format, and produce reproducible force field files that include both the model and its metadata.

Manually creating an input file involves locating all relevant information within a given publication, mapping it to the simulation engine’s data scheme and format, and, if necessary, converting units (cf. Figure 2-right). Potentially, also coordinates have to be transformed to different coordinate systems, e.g. converting from Cartesian to Z-matrix coordinates. Evidently, units, notations, and conventions have to be interpreted correctly for extracting force field information. Ambiguities or missing details frequently require additional effort to resolve in the traditional manual route and transcription into the precise syntax and unit system required by the simulation engine introduces further opportunities for error. Also the validation of the constructed input file is not trivial since simulation benchmark data are often scarce. As a result, preparing even a single ready-to-use input file can consume a considerable amount of time if manually done, e.g. some hours by an experienced simulator. Autonomous extraction using LLM offers an alternative by performing the same mapping and formatting tasks automatically and at scale, greatly reducing the effort required to reuse published force fields. In the autonomous method developed in this work, all these steps are

carried out by the LLM.

Autonomous Force Field Extraction from Scientific Publications

The proposed approach automates the traditionally manual task of transcribing force field data from research papers into force field files. By reducing human involvement, the method circumvents user-induced transcription errors and accelerates data preparation. The workflow of the method, illustrated in Figure 2, progresses through the five steps, which are detailed in the following subsections.

Step 1: Optical Character Recognition (OCR)

The process begins by selecting a research paper, typically in `.pdf` format, as input. Many `.pdf` files, especially older scanned ones, store text as images rather than selectable characters. To make the content usable by our method, the first step is to apply optical character recognition (OCR). For this purpose, we employ the *mistral-ocr-2505* model from Mistral AI,⁶⁷ which acts as a digital reader by analyzing each page image, identifying the shapes of letters and numbers, and converting them into machine-readable text. Conceptually, this step transforms the visual representation of the document into structured textual data that subsequent steps of the pipeline process.

Step 2: Text Cleaning

The raw text obtained from OCR often contains non-essential elements. Therefore, a text cleaning is applied. In this step, the system processes the raw digital text (as shown in Figure 3-a.) to remove artifacts that are not part of the main textual content or tables relevant for parameter extraction. This includes filtering out footers, bibliography, metadata, and other content that does not contain relevant data. The purpose of cleaning is to ensure that only the core scientific text and data tables are passed on to the next step, preventing interference in subsequent analysis steps. An example of extracted text after text cleaning

is illustrated in Figure 3-b. In this example, the remaining text includes all sections from the paper from introduction to conclusion.

Step 3: Table Detection

In scientific publications, content of a force field can be presented in tables, figures, or in plain text. Moreover, multiple force fields can be specified in a single paper. The most frequent representation of force field information is tables, which we focus on in the developed extraction method. Step three focuses on table detection. Using rule-based pattern matching techniques, the system scans the cleaned text specifically looking for structures that resemble tables. This involves searching for textual cues, such as captions explicitly labeling a table (e.g., "Table 1", "Table II"), and recognizing the characteristic grid-like layout often formed by columns separated by spaces or vertical lines (i.e. |). By identifying these patterns, the method can distinguish tables from narrative paragraphs and extract their content while preserving the essential row and column structure. This results in two sets of data: The main body text and the structured content of the detected tables.

Step 4: Data Extraction

Having the cleaned text and identified tables accessible, the actual data extraction is carried out in step 4. Here, the large language models (LLMs)⁵⁰ are employed. Several LLMs were tested and compared as described below. Instead of programming explicit rules for every possible parameter, we provide the LLM with carefully crafted instructions, i.e. a prompt. This prompt guides the LLM, telling it to act as an expert in molecular modeling and instructing it on exactly what information to find (e.g. chemical names, specific parameters like σ , ϵ , dipole moment etc.) and how to format this information according to the syntax of the .pm file format.

The .pm file format uses Cartesian coordinates. In many force field publications, Cartesian coordinates of interaction sites are not provided directly; instead, structural information

is often given in terms of distances and angles between sites (e.g. the Z-matrix form). Since the `.pm` format requires Cartesian coordinates, the LLM is tasked with producing x, y, z positions even when only Z-matrix data are available, without receiving explicit instructions on how to perform this translation. The correct unit system is also specified in the prompt (e.g., dipole moments μ must be expressed in Debye). Importantly, no additional metadata such as the total number of force fields in a publication or the number of interaction sites is inferred beyond what is explicitly reported.

The data extraction process is illustrated in Figure 4. Along with the prompt, the cleaned text and extracted tables are provided to the LLM as context. The LLM then reads this context and uses its understanding of language and instructions to locate the relevant values and populate the required `.pm` file structure, associating the correct values with their corresponding parameters (e.g. linking a numerical value from a table column to the correct parameter name like ‘sigma’ or ‘dipole’ for a specific chemical site). This process resembles instructing an expert assistant to fill out a detailed form using information found within a document.

Step 5: Writing Force Field File

The final stage of the pipeline is the generation of simulation-ready `.pm` files. After the extraction step, the parameters are organized into a standardized format that can be directly used in a molecular simulation software or force field database. During this process, the method retrieves the title of the source publication together with the names of the identified substances, which are included in the file header to preserve provenance and traceability. For each substance, a separate `.pm` file is created that comprises the generated header with the cleaned and structured parameter content of the force field. The parameters are annotated according to the interaction site type. Thus, the resulting files encode not only the molecular model itself but also the associated metadata.

Validation

Validation Procedure and Test Set

To assess the accuracy and reliability of the autonomous digitization method, we tested multiple LLMs and papers for extracting force field data and creating `.pm` files. The content of the autonomously created force field files were systematically compared against manually curated ground-truth reference files taken from Ref.³⁶ Based on a comprehensive evaluation of the results, individual shortcomings of the new method were identified which also provides insights in the inner workings of the LLM approach.

We employed five state-of-the-art LLMs: Gemini 2.5 Pro,⁶⁸ Claude 4 Sonnet,⁶⁹ GPT-4o,⁷⁰ Claude 3.7 Sonnet,⁷¹ and Gemini 2.5 Flash.⁶⁸ A brief description of the characteristics of these models is provided in Table 1. With the exception of the GPT-4o model, which was introduced in 2024, all other models were released in 2025. The selected LLMs share several core characteristics. They are all proprietary models with undisclosed parameter counts, reflecting a trend in commercial LLM developing to focus on capability disclosures rather than architectural transparency. The models differ in modality support, context window size, and output capacity. Gemini 2.5 Pro and Gemini 2.5 Flash offer the largest publicly stated context limits, clearly surpassing limits of the other employed models. The maximum output length also varies, with Gemini 2.5 Pro/Flash and the Claude models supporting the similarly large tokens number, whereas GPT-4o supports significantly smaller values (cf. Table 1). These differences suggest that the five models are optimized for different operational tasks and their results may therefore vary significantly on specific tasks.

For testing and validating the developed method, we selected a set of 21 scientific publications comprising in total 114 force field models. The publications were selected based on the force field compilation in the MolMod database^{36,37} covering force fields from more than 200 publications. Only publications with rigid component-specific force fields were considered here. Table 2 gives an overview of the $N_{\text{pub}} = 21$ publications used in the test

(the numbering column 'No' is used throughout this work for referring to specific papers). This entity is a diverse compilation covering a wide range of year of publication, number of force fields in a given paper, research groups developing the models, molecule size etc. The number of force field models N_M per paper ranges from 1 to 62. Figure 5 shows histograms of properties of the studied force fields, i.e. number of interaction sites per force field N_S and number of parameters per force field N_P . For the actual evaluation of the digitization method, the .pm files stored in the MolMod database were used as the ground truth.

Algorithm 1 shows the evaluation workflow. The algorithm iterates over each ground-truth parameter, checking whether the model output contains the correct value, an incorrect value, or no value at all. Based on these checks, the proportion of correct matches is computed, returning both the accuracy percentage and detailed counts for correct, incorrect, and missing parameters. Thus, we calculated three categories of values: correct, incorrect, and missing. Incorrect values contain some type of recognition error, while missing values have not been identified at all. In the following, any deviation from the corresponding reference value is considered incorrect (termed 'Numeric Value Mismatch').

For the evaluation, four different metrics measures were used: Average accuracy (*Avg Acc*), precision (P), recall (R), and $F1$ -score.⁷² We also report the number of correct (N_{correct}), incorrect ($N_{\text{incorrect}}$), and missing (N_{missing}) force field parameter values which are aggregated totals of parameters across all papers and runs.

The per-paper parameter extraction accuracy by model and run is calculated as

$$Acc = \frac{1}{N_{\text{pub}}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{pub}}} \frac{N_{\text{correct}}}{N_{\text{correct}} + N_{\text{incorrect}} + N_{\text{missing}}}. \quad (5)$$

The average accuracy is calculated as the mean accuracy over all papers as

$$Avg\ Acc = \frac{1}{N_{\text{pub}}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{pub}}} \frac{N_{\text{correct}}}{N_{\text{correct}} + N_{\text{incorrect}} + N_{\text{missing}}}. \quad (6)$$

Precision (P) measures the fraction of retrieved parameters that are correct and is computed

from the aggregate totals as

$$P = \frac{N_{\text{correct}}}{N_{\text{correct}} + N_{\text{incorrect}}}. \quad (7)$$

Recall (R) quantifies the fraction of correct parameters that were successfully retrieved in relation to missing parameters as

$$R = \frac{N_{\text{correct}}}{N_{\text{correct}} + N_{\text{missing}}}. \quad (8)$$

The $F1$ -score is an aggregated measure of the precision and recall and is defined as the harmonic mean of these

$$F1 = 2 \frac{P \cdot R}{P + R}. \quad (9)$$

High values of precision and recall (close to 1) indicate strong performance. Deviations from unity highlight different types of errors: Precision decreases when parameters are retrieved but incorrect, whereas recall decreases when parameters are not retrieved at all. The $F1$ -score balances these two measures, which can be particularly useful when precision and recall do not correlate or inversely correlate.

The digitization method was run three times for each studied LLM. These runs were independent, i.e. single end-to-end executions for a given paper and model using identical inputs, prompts, and hyperparameters; runs were isolated and differ only due to model stochasticity (e.g. sampling seed).

Results

Table 3 summarizes the performance results of the different LLM regarding the average accuracy, precision, recall, and $F1$ -score. Gemini 2.5 Pro achieved the highest average accuracy at 89.1%. Claude 3.7 Sonnet and Claude 4 Sonnet followed with average accuracies of 86.3%

and 85.2%, respectively. Gemini 2.5 Flash (78.0%) and GPT-4o (76.2%) yield poorer performance, highlighting potential trade-offs between model architecture and extraction quality. The analysis of correct, incorrect, and missing values shows that Claude 4 Sonnet achieved the highest percentage of correct values (91%), closely followed by Gemini 2.5 Pro (90%), significantly exceeding the average across all models. We categorized extraction outputs into correct, incorrect, and missing parameters using the validation procedure described in Algorithm 1. Claude 4 Sonnet and Gemini 2.5 Pro yield the highest share of correct extractions (91% and 90%, respectively) and the lowest share of incorrect assignments (8% and 9%). In contrast, GPT-4o exhibits the highest rate of incorrect values (24%), followed by Gemini 2.5 Flash (19%), suggesting greater 'confusion' in parameter interpretation of the AI models. The share of missing values remained relatively consistent and low across models, ranging from 0-1%. This is in line with results reported by *Polak and Morgan*⁵⁴ who studied the extraction of materials data from publications and obtaining precision and recall values also around 90%. In their work, the LLMs retrieved materials properties as structured triplets of three values and the performance was achieved in part by asking follow-up questions and explicitly retrieving information on the uncertainty of the extracted data.

The execution time of the autonomous algorithm is similar for the different LLMs, which is significantly shorter than the time a human would require to extract the information, apply any necessary conversions, and create a `.pm` file. While it is impressive that `.pm` files can be in general constructed from `.pdf` files using LLM, the average accuracy of nearly 90% (for the best performing model Gemini 2.5 Pro) is not sufficient for directly employing the constructed force field files in a molecular simulation. This would essentially require a reliable accuracy of 100%.

Figure 6 shows the extraction accuracy per paper averaged over three runs for each model. The overall mean accuracy and the range of scattering of the different LLM is depicted in Figure 7. Gemini 2.5 Pro regularly achieves the highest or near-highest score in most papers. In several cases, this model achieved even an accuracy of 100%, which also holds for some

other LLM. Claude 3.7 Sonnet and Claude 4 Sonnet follow as the next-best performers, delivering consistently good results with only a marginal difference between them. Gemini 2.5 Flash and GPT-4o, lag behind, consistently underperforming the aforementioned LLM across the evaluated papers. Possibly, the superior accuracy of Gemini 2.5 Pro stems from its design as a high-reasoning model, which allocates more computation during inference to produce robust and well-reasoned responses.⁶⁸ In contrast, Gemini 2.5 Flash is optimized for speed and efficiency,⁶⁸ making it less suited for tasks that demand strong generalization and domain knowledge, although it may be suitable for applications where processing speed is a critical factor.

For all employed LLM, the obtained accuracy differs for different papers, cf. Figure 6 and 7. This scattering is largest for GPT-4o and smallest for Gemini 2.5 Pro. Interestingly, this is in line with the relative accuracy of the studied LLMs. Moreover, the performance of the LLMs for a given paper differs in parts significantly, e.g. Gemini 2.5 Pro yields excellent results for papers #1 and #4 for which Claude 3.7 Sonnet yields relatively poor results. For paper #8, on the other hand, Claude 3.7 Sonnet outperforms Gemini 2.5 Pro.

Figure 8 shows per-paper, per-run accuracy results for each model, with the global best across models shown in the background. In some cases, the results from the three independent runs are practically identical, e.g. for the #9 results from Gemini 2.5 Pro. In other cases, significantly different results are obtained from the three independent runs, e.g. for the #8 results from Gemini 2.5 Pro. Gemini 2.5 Pro frequently meets or approaches the global best, reinforcing its leading placement. Claude 3.7 Sonnet and Claude 4 Sonnet follow closely, with occasional drops. The remaining models (GPT-4o and Gemini 2.5 Flash) reveal specific papers where the extraction accuracy is significantly lower.

For establishing a better understanding of the nature of the extraction errors, we performed a detailed analysis of 6,049 errors across all employed LLM models, replica runs, force fields, and papers, using the error types defined in Table 4. The distribution, shown in Table 5, reveals that the two most dominant error types are "Numeric Value Mismatch"

(42.0% of all errors) and "Zero Coordinate Error" (17.0%). Together, these account for 59% of all extraction errors. Other significant error types include "Count/Index Error" (8.0%), "Rotation Parameter Error" (7.2%), and "Placeholder Value Error" (6.4%).

Furthermore, specific force fields parameters that were most frequently extracted incorrectly are summarized in Table 6. Basic physical properties such as 'mass' were the most common source of error, followed by atomic coordinates ('z', 'y', 'x'). The errors associated with 'mass' were primarily "Numeric Value Mismatch" and "Placeholder Value Error". Coordinates were susceptible to being incorrectly zeroed ("Zero Coordinate Error") or having their values mismatched ("Coordinate Extraction Error"). Less frequent but still notable errors included 'Sign Error' for parameters like 'charge' and 'Categorical Misclassification' for symbolic labels like site types.

Conclusions

LLM provide a remarkably fast and robust route for digitizing force field models from publications. The autonomous data extraction pipeline proposed in this work transforms a the model data comprised in research paper .pdf files into structured, simulation-ready .pm files. This automated approach offers a significant improvement over manual methods, enhancing efficiency and reducing the potential for human errors in preparing molecular simulation inputs. The accuracy of the autonomous method is roughly 75 to 90% – depending on the employed LLM. Accurate and reproducible molecular simulations demand 100% accuracy, i.e. force field input files without any error. Thus, the method and results from this paper should be seen as a starting point for developing a reliable and autonomous digitization tool. The method proposed in this work is an attractive alternative to tedious and error-prone "by hand" digitization of force fields for molecular simulations.

Possible ways to improve the accuracy of the digitization method can be guided from the experiences from the comprehensive evaluation carried out in this work. These results

provide a robust benchmark for testing refinements and improvements. A large variety of routes to improve the promising results from this work seem attractive. On the one hand, the prompt may be further refined as to give more context in the translation between Z-matrix and Cartesian coordinates or by providing more physical background/information. The error analysis revealed that numeric mismatches and zero coordinate errors are the most frequent error types, which most frequently occur for the coordinates and the mass. On the other hand, OCR is not 100% error-free and newer, even stronger LLMs might handle this task even better. Additionally, LLMs with greater variability or higher error rates may benefit from ensembling, further prompt adaptation, or supplementary rule-based checks. Moreover, another interesting approach would be to use different LLMs sequentially.

The results from this work show that larger, more capable models^{68,69,71} (Gemini 2.5 Pro, Claude 3.7, and 4 Sonnet) yield an overall more accurate extraction of force field data from scientific publications. The overall best performance was achieved by the Gemini 2.5 Pro LLM with an accuracy rate of 89.1%. Performance variability across papers and occasional outliers further highlight the need to study model stability and generalization in more detail.

Furthermore, the comprehensive evaluation of the new method provided insights in challenges in force field publication in the scientific literature: Different unit systems are used in different publications (and communities); different coordinate systems are used (Z-matrix, Cartesian etc.); Information on a given force field are often scattered across a publication with some data given in the bulk text, some in tables, and sometimes even graphics. Sometimes, no spatial coordinates are specified, but have to be determined as the equilibrium configuration from the stated intramolecular interactions. Moreover, there is no universal and standardized force field data format established yet. These insights highlight not only the need for more advanced extraction methods but also for community-wide standards and publication practices to make force fields consistently reusable.

Supporting Information Available

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at [LINK](#).

Acknowledgement

The authors gratefully acknowledge funding of the present work by the Federal Ministry of Research, Technology and Space (BMFTR, Germany) 16ME0613 WindHPC and from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No. 101137725 (BatCAT). Simulations for validation were carried out on the ELWE supercomputer at Regional University Computing Center Kaiserslautern (RHRZ) under the grant RPTU-MTD and on the HPC machine MOGON NHR at the NHR SW under the grant TUK-MSG (supported by the Federal Ministry of Research, Technology and Space and the state governments).

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest to declare.

Data Availability

The python pipeline developed within this work is provided in the Supporting Information. Moreover, the force field `.pm` files built within this work using the LLMs are provided as well as the reference `.pm` files that were built 'by hand'.

Author contribution statement

Florian Fleckenstein: Data Curation, Formal Analysis (equal), Software (equal), Visualization (equal), Writing/Original Draft Preparation (equal); Volodymyr Rodin: Data Curation,

Formal Analysis (equal), Software (equal), Visualization (equal), Writing/Original Draft Preparation (equal); Isabell Dieudonne: Data Curation (support), Software; Fadi Al Machot: Writing/Review & Editing (support); Silvia Chiacchiera: Writing/Review & Editing (support); Martin Horsch: Writing/Review & Editing (support); Amila Akagic: Conceptualization (equal), Methodology (equal), Supervision (equal), Writing/Original Draft Preparation (lead); Simon Stephan: Conceptualization (equal), Methodology (equal), Supervision (equal), Writing/Original Draft Preparation (lead), Funding Acquisition (equal).

Figures & Tables

Table 1: Technical specifications of employed LLMs.

Model	Modality	Max context / tokens	Max output / tokens
Gemini 2.5 Pro ⁶⁸	Text, Vision, Audio, Video	1,048,576	65,535
Claude 4 Sonnet ⁶⁹	Text, Vision	200,000	64,000
Claude 3.7 Sonnet ⁷¹	Text, Vision	200,000	64,000
Gemini 2.5 Flash ⁶⁸	Text, Vision, Audio, Video	1,048,576	65,535
GPT-4o ⁷⁰	Text, Vision, Audio	128,000	16,384

Table 2: List of publications used in the validation data set. The columns indicate the publication identifier number (used throughout this work), year and number of force field models (N_M) in a given paper.

No.	Paper	Year	N_M	No.	Paper	Year	N_M
1	<i>Eckl et al.</i> ⁷³	2007	1	12	<i>Abbas & Nordholm</i> ⁷⁴	1995	3
2	<i>Horsch et al.</i> ⁷⁵	2010	1	13	<i>Eckelsbach et al.</i> ⁷⁶	2015	1
3	<i>Kohns et al.</i> ⁷⁷	2017	2	14	<i>Eckl et al.</i> ⁷⁸	2008	10
4	<i>Köster et al.</i> ⁷⁹	2018	1	15	<i>Fischer et al.</i> ⁸⁰	1984	7
5	<i>Merker et al.</i> ⁸¹	2010	1	16	<i>Gao et al.</i> ⁸²	1997	8
6	<i>Merker et al.</i> ⁸³	2012	2	17	<i>Koyama et al.</i> ⁸⁴	2005	1
7	<i>Miroshnichenko et al.</i> ⁸⁵	2013	2	18	<i>Romano & Singer</i> ⁶⁵	1979	2
8	<i>Muñoz-Muñoz et al.</i> ⁸⁶	2017	3	19	<i>Zhang & Siepmann</i> ⁸⁷	2006	1
9	<i>Muñoz-Muñoz et al.</i> ⁸⁸	2018	1	20	<i>de Santis et al.</i> ⁸⁹	1987	3
10	<i>Vrabec & Fischer</i> ⁹⁰	1995	1	21	<i>van Leeuwen</i> ⁹¹	1994	62
11	<i>Windmann et al.</i> ⁶⁶	2014	1				

Table 3: Summary of performance metrics results for studied LLMs. Average accuracy is computed by calculating mean accuracy over papers; correct/incorrect/missing counts are aggregate totals of parameters across all papers and runs.

Model	Avg Acc / %	Prec / %	Rec / %	F1 / %	Correct	Incorrect	Missing
Gemini 2.5 Pro	89.1	91.0	99.2	94.9	7382 (90%)	733 (9%)	63 (1%)
Claude 4 Sonnet	85.2	92.4	98.9	95.5	7467 (91%)	618 (8%)	81 (1%)
Claude 3.7 Sonnet	86.3	89.1	99.3	93.9	7232 (89%)	883 (11%)	51 (1%)
Gemini 2.5 Flash	78.0	81.2	99.7	89.5	6618 (81%)	1531 (19%)	17 (0%)
GPT-4o	76.2	75.5	98.5	85.5	6094 (75%)	1978 (24%)	94 (1%)
Average	-	-	-	-	- (85%)	- (14%)	- (1%)

Table 4: Classification of extraction errors observed in incorrect results across evaluated datasets. Examples are shown in the format *reference* \rightarrow *extracted*.

Error Type	Description	Example (Reference \rightarrow Extracted)
Numeric Value Mismatch	Extracted numeric value differs significantly from reference.	<code>mass = 127.91241</code> \rightarrow <code>36.46</code> (Abbas, 1995) ⁷⁴
Zero Coordinate Error	Non-zero coordinates incorrectly replaced with 0.0.	<code>z = -0.232</code> \rightarrow <code>0.0</code> (de Santis, 1987) ⁸⁹
Count/Index Error	Wrong extraction of discrete counts (sites, site types).	<code>NsiteTypes = 2</code> \rightarrow <code>8</code> (Munoz-Munoz, 2017) ⁸⁶
Rotation Parameter Error	Misextraction of rotational inertia, angles, or axes.	<code>theta = 30.0</code> \rightarrow <code>45.0</code> (Gao, 1997) ⁸²
Placeholder Value Error	Values replaced with placeholder tokens like [MASS_VALUE].	<code>mass = 12.011</code> \rightarrow <code>[MASS_VALUE]</code> (de Santis, 1987) ⁸⁹
Coordinate Extraction Error	Incorrect coordinates (non-zero to non-zero).	<code>z = -0.232</code> \rightarrow <code>1.185</code> (de Santis, 1987) ⁸⁹
Missing Parameter	Parameter completely absent from extraction.	<code>mass = 16.042</code> \rightarrow <code>(missing)</code> (Koyama, 2005) ⁸⁴
Physical Property Misread	Misreading of physical properties (charges, dipoles, etc.).	<code>dipole = 3.228</code> \rightarrow <code>1.988</code> (Gao, 1997) ⁸²
Categorical Misclassification	Site types or labels incorrectly classified.	<code>SiteType = Dipole</code> \rightarrow <code>LJ126</code> (Munoz-Munoz, 2017) ⁸⁶
Sign Error	Correct magnitude with wrong or missing sign.	<code>charge = +0.2556</code> \rightarrow <code>0.2556</code> (Horsch, 2010) ⁷⁵
Other	Uncategorized errors (mostly unusual formats).	<code>mass = 13.019</code> \rightarrow <code>#CH</code> (Horsch, 2010) ⁷⁵

Table 5: Distribution of extraction error types across 6,049 total errors from 21 scientific papers for all force fields and replica runs.

Error Type	Count	%	Num of Papers Affected
Numeric Value Mismatch	2,539	42.0%	21
Zero Coordinate Error	1,031	17.0%	13
Count/Index Error	481	8.0%	16
Rotation Parameter Error	438	7.2%	10
Placeholder Value Error	385	6.4%	21
Coordinate Extraction Error	379	6.3%	13
Missing Parameter	306	5.1%	21
Physical Property Misread	297	4.9%	4
Categorical Misclassification	97	1.6%	8
Sign Error	72	1.2%	5
Other	24	0.4%	21
Total	6,049		

Table 6: Molecular parameters most frequently extracted incorrectly, showing the 15 variables with the highest error counts.

Variable	Error Count	%	Primary Error Types
mass	2,239	37.0%	Numeric Value Mismatch, Placeholder Value Error
z	638	10.5%	Zero Coordinate Error, Coordinate Extraction Error
y	506	8.4%	Zero Coordinate Error, Coordinate Extraction Error
NSiteTypes	365	6.0%	Count/Index Error
theta	354	5.9%	Rotation Parameter Error
x	320	5.3%	Zero Coordinate Error, Coordinate Extraction Error, Missing Parameter
charge	310	5.1%	Missing Parameter, Sign Error
epsilon	293	4.8%	Missing Parameter, Numeric Value Mismatch
dipole	271	4.5%	Missing Parameter, Physical Property Misread
sigma	235	3.9%	Missing Parameter, Numeric Value Mismatch
phi	228	3.8%	Rotation Parameter Error
NSites	121	2.0%	Count/Index Error, Missing Parameter
SiteType	99	1.6%	Categorical Misclassification, Missing Parameter
quadrupole	31	0.5%	Physical Property Misread, Placeholder Value Error
MIE_n	15	0.2%	Missing Parameter

Figure 1: Schematic representation of two exemplary chosen molecular force field models with corresponding geometric, mass, and interaction parameters. Left: Chlorine model of *Romano & Singer*.⁶⁵ Right: Acetone model of *Windmann et al.*⁶⁶ The total number of parameters is 15 for chlorine (including 12 geometric, mass, and interaction parameters and 3 parameters required for the given file format used within the simulation engine) and 48 for acetone (including 36 geometric, mass, and interaction parameters and 12 parameters required for the given file format used within the simulation engine).

Figure 2: Overview of the automated data extraction pipeline (left) and the manual extraction process (right). Large Language Model (LLM) workflow: A research paper .pdf file is uploaded (Step 1) and OCR is used to retrieve and structure the text. The raw text is cleaned (Step 2) to remove nonessential artifacts, then rule-based pattern matching detects and extracts tables from the cleaned text (Step 3). Structured text and tables are merged for molecular parameter extraction (Step 4), and those parameters are verified in a validation stage (Step 5). The validated data is finally formatted and written as simulation-ready .pm file. Manual Process: Reading, scanning, and locating relevant information within the publication, mapping it to the simulation engine’s data scheme and format, and, if necessary, converting units. The data is then manually transferred to the .pm file and validated.

```

Raw OCR excerpt
# Vapor pressure of R227ea + ethanol...
Bernhard Eckl, Yow-Lin Huang, Jadran
Vrabec*...
Received 27 February 2007...

#### Abstract
A new molecular model for...

## 1. Introduction
The vapor pressure prediction for the
binary mixture
1,1,1,2,3,3,3-heptafluoropropane +
ethanol at 343.13 K has been selected
by the Industrial Fluid Properties
Simulation Collective...
...
For that purpose, a new molecular model
for 1,1,1,2,3,3,3-heptafluoropropane
was developed here.

## References
[1] Industrial Fluid Properties...

```

(a) Original OCR output with all metadata and the complete cleaned text preserved.

```

Cleaned text
## 1. Introduction

The vapor pressure prediction for the
binary mixture
1,1,1,2,3,3,3-heptafluoropropane +
ethanol at 343.13 K has been selected
by the Industrial Fluid Properties
Simulation Collective...
...
For that purpose, a new molecular model
for 1,1,1,2,3,3,3-heptafluoropropane
was developed here.

```

(b) After cleaning: only the core narrative is retained; header, abstract, and references are stripped.

Figure 3: Text cleaning example: left now retains all content including what's in the cleaned version, while right shows only the stripped version.

Figure 4: Schematic representation of workflow: Cleaned text and the structured tables are fed, along with an expertly crafted prompt, into an LLM which acts as a molecular modeling expert and outputs a .pm file with extracted parameters (Lennard-Jones site, dipole, and quadrupole with orientations etc.).

Figure 5: Histograms of number of interactions sites N_S (left) and force field parameters N_P (right) of the 114 studied force field models.

Algorithm 1 Core Parameter Validation Logic

```
1: procedure VALIDATEEXTRACTION(GroundTruthParams, ModelOutputText)
2:   ▷ GroundTruthParams is a list of (parameter, value) pairs from the reference file.
3:   ▷ ModelOutputText is the full text content generated by the model.
4:
5:   Correct ← 0
6:   Incorrect ← 0
7:   Missing ← 0
8:
9:   for all (param, expected_value) in GroundTruthParams do
10:    if ModelOutputText contains "param = expected_value" then
11:      Correct ← Correct + 1
12:    else if ModelOutputText contains "param = some other value" then
13:      Incorrect ← Incorrect + 1
14:    else
15:      Missing ← Missing + 1
16:    end if
17:  end for
18:
19:  Total ← count of GroundTruthParams
20:  Accuracy ← (Correct/Total) × 100
21:
22:  return Accuracy, Correct, Incorrect, Missing
23: end procedure
```

Figure 6: Per-paper extraction accuracy (cf. Eq. 5) averaged over three runs for each LLM. The color code indicates the accuracy.

Figure 7: Model accuracy with run-to-run variability. Error bars indicate the variation across three independent runs, representing the mean performance between the best- and worst-performing runs for each paper.

Figure 8: Per-paper parameter extraction accuracy by model and run (cf. Eq. 5), with the global best across models indicated in the blue background. Each group of three red bars for a paper represents the results from three individual runs of a given LLM.

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

**Autonomous extraction and building
of machine-readable molecular models
from publications using large
language models**

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2025-09-22

Supporting Information Contents

The Supporting Information for the publication *Autonomous extraction and building of machine-readable molecular models from publications using large language models* contains the following components:

- Manually curated reference `.pm` files serving as ground truth for accuracy evaluation (given in the electronic Supporting Information),
- Examples of automatically generated `.pm` files produced by the LLM-based extraction pipeline (given in the electronic Supporting Information),
- Complete Jupyter notebook (`molecular_engineering_openrouter.ipynb`) implementing the five-step digitization method.

Running the Colab Notebook

The electronic Supporting Information includes a Jupyter notebook (`molecular_engineering_openrouter4.ipynb`) that implements the complete digitization pipeline described below. To reproduce the results or process new publications, follow these configuration steps:

API Key Configuration

The notebook requires two API keys for the external services used in the pipeline:

Mistral OCR API Key

In Section 2 (Cell 4), replace the placeholder API key in the following line:

```
client = Mistral(api_key="YOUR_MISTRAL_API_KEY_HERE")
```

OpenRouter API Key

In Section 7 (Cell with "Run Parameter Extraction"), replace the placeholder API key:

```
api_key = "YOUR_OPENROUTER_API_KEY_HERE"
```

Directory Configuration

Set the `extract_dir` variable to point to your directory containing PDF files:

For OCR Processing (Section 2)

Modify the directory path in Cell 5:

```
extract_dir = "path/to/your/papers"
```

For Parameter Extraction (Section 7)

Update the extraction directory in the same section:

```
extract_dir = "path/to/your/papers"
```

For Evaluation and Visualization (Sections 9 and 11)

Ensure the directory path is consistent in both evaluation sections:

```
extract_dir = "path/to/your/papers"
```

Model Selection and File Pattern Configuration

Model Selection (Section 7)

Specify the desired LLM for parameter extraction by modifying the `selected_model` variable:

```
selected_model = "anthropic/claude-3.7-sonnet"
```

```
selected_model = "google/gemini-2.5-pro"
```

```
selected_model = "openai/gpt-4o"
```

Evaluation File Pattern (Section 8)

After running Section 7, update the file pattern in Section 8 to match the generated extraction files. Modify line 23 in the `find_files_to_compare` function:

```
extraction_files = glob.glob(os.path.join(subfolder_path,  
    "*_openrouter_[model_name]_[version].txt"))
```

Replace `[model_name]` and `[version]` with the actual values from your extraction run (e.g., `*_openrouter_anthropic_claude-sonnet-4_3.txt`).

PM File Generation Pattern (Section 6)

For generating `.pm` files from extraction results, update the model pattern in the `generate_pm_files_from_extractions` function call:

```
generated_files = generate_pm_files_from_extractions(  
    extract_dir,  
    model_pattern="*_openrouter_[model_name]_[version].txt"  
)
```

Execution Order

Execute the notebook sections sequentially:

1. Section 1: Upload and extract PDF files
2. Section 2: OCR processing with Mistral AI
3. Sections 3-6: Text cleaning and table extraction
4. Section 7: Parameter extraction with selected LLM
5. Section 8: Configure evaluation file patterns based on Section 7 output

6. Section 9: Accuracy evaluation against reference files

7. Sections 10-11: Visualization of results

The notebook automatically handles file naming conventions, ensuring that extraction results are properly matched with reference files during evaluation. Output files follow the naming pattern `[paper]_openrouter_[model]_[version].txt`, enabling systematic comparison across different models and multiple runs. The model name and version number in the filename must be updated in the evaluation and PM generation sections to match the files produced by the parameter extraction step. the files produced by the parameter extraction step.